

**THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY COMMUNICATION IN
THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE
IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF TOURISM
DIRECTIONS)**

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Annotation: We are talking about the formation of communicative competence, i.e. ability and readiness to carry out direct communication (speaking, listening comprehension) and indirect communication (reading, writing foreign texts with understanding). This article discusses the importance of interdisciplinary communication in the development of students' professional competence in English (in the case of tourism destinations).

Keywords: communication, professional competence, tourism direction, teaching foreign languages, communication, speaking ability, integration, communication sciences, methodology, oral communication.

Formation of communicative competence of tourism students is the main and leading goal of education. Today it is especially popular. The greatest difficulties in communication in a foreign language are experienced by a person when receiving speech by ear. However, oral communication, the role of which is particularly important now, is impossible without understanding the speech of the interlocutor, because in the process of speech interaction, everyone works as both a speaker and a listener. One of the most controversial aspects of the problem of teaching tourism students foreign languages is the methodology of checking and taking into account knowledge, skills and qualifications, their organization and implementation. Control has not yet become a "powerful lever" for improving

educational activity and a source that helps to determine the actual state of knowledge and skills in a given subject.

The effective appearance of speech activity is carried out through oral communication (along with listening). The content of speech is the expression of thought in oral form. Speech is based on pronunciation, lexical, grammatical skills. Speaking is one of the most important areas of teaching in many teaching methods. According to the major or minor role of programming, the statements distinguish initiative (active) speech, reactive (response) speech, reproductive (stochastic) speech. The psychological structure of the speech act includes four stages:

1) motivating motivational, in which the person's need for communication is manifested under the influence of a certain motive and the presence of a certain purpose of the statement;

2) analytic-synthetic, presented in the form of folded mental actions for programming and forming thoughts (there is a mechanism for the internal formation of a statement that ensures the selection of words and grammatical forecasting);

3) The executive sound and intonation design of thought (at the initial stage of learning, the transition of the speech program to its implementation occurs through the native language;

4) control, his task is to signal possible errors and contribute to their correction; control implies that the speaker has a norm that is formed as a result of language practice and comparison of his speech with the norm.

In particular, the following methods should be implemented to develop the English language competence of students studying tourism:

The principle of speech orientation. The speech direction of the educational process is not only a practical goal in speech, but the way to this goal is a very practical use of the language. The direction of practical speech is not only a goal, but also unity. The direction of the speech implies the eloquence of exercises, i.e. degree, the criterion of their speech similarity. All of them should be exercises not

in pronunciation, but in speech, when the speaker has a clear task and when he makes a speech effect on the interlocutor.

The principle of speech orientation also includes the use of communicatively valuable speech material. The use of each expression should be justified by taking into account the intended area of communication (situation) and the communicative value for this category of students. The speech character of the lesson also plays an important role here.

The principle of individualization with the leading role of his personal aspect. Individualization takes into account all the characteristics of tourism students as individuals: their abilities, ability to perform speech and educational activities, and mainly their personal characteristics. Individualization is the main realistic means of creating motivation and activity. A person expresses his attitude to the environment in speech. And since this relationship is always individual, therefore speech is individual. In teaching speech in a foreign language, an individual reaction is possible if the speech task before the student meets his needs and interests as a person. Any statement by the student should be as natural as possible.

Principle of functionality. Any speech unit performs in the process. Communication of any speech functions. Often, after a course of study, students know words and grammatical forms, but they cannot use all of them in speech, because not. transfer occurs (speech functions performed by words and forms when they are pre-filled separately, the word or form is not related to speech). Functionality, first of all, determines the selection and organization of material suitable for the communication process. The approach to communication needs is possible only if the means of speech are taken into account and the material is organized around situations and speech tasks rather than around topics of conversation and grammatical events. Unity of lexical, grammatical and phonetic aspects of speech is also necessary.

Social relations are mainly carried out in the country of the language being studied. A person who has learned a language based on them will probably be able

to communicate in the specific conditions of the country where the language is being studied. This knowledge is almost unnecessary when communicating with foreigners in our country.

The speech activity of tourism students is based on the transfer of skills, because the endlessly changing conditions of communication impose new tasks on the speaker every time. If the speaking skills underlying the competence are potentially transferable and therefore the speaking skills are dynamic enough, they can be tackled. Conditional speech situations are a condition for the formation of situational flexibility of speech skills. They create all the conditions for a certain speech unit, in special conditions suitable for the automation of a speech pattern (regularity of use, exemplary), without losing the situation (usually typical of training exercises).

The situation is a prerequisite for the development of skills. Let's say that the need to convince someone of something, naturally, can arise only if the situation is not imposed from the outside, but if it is a consequence or a precursor of the events in which the interlocutors participated. The broader and deeper the connection of a particular situation with all activity, the easier the motive appears: the content of consciousness is human activity.

A very good context for the activity can be provided by special films. These event films should be communicative in content (problem), direction (taking into account the field of communication), and have a methodological character. Such a film is shown before each lesson cycle and introduces students to the environment of the next events, based on which the teacher creates situations in the classroom.

During English classes, some tourism students do not know how to apply and do not use technology, which leads to some boredom of students. It is for this reason that in order not to extinguish the enthusiasm of the learner, the use of technology and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the interest of the learner increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these

requirements, if we broadcast video films, songs or texts containing complex words to elementary school students, or if we show them through multimedia, computers, when we present teaching materials with very simple texts to elementary and high school students or groups, the students' interest in learning the language gradually fades and they don't master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a drop in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in front of the students.

For example, in the listening and comprehension classes of tourism students, there are rules for playing audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he is listening to and be able to analyze it without difficulty. For this, the first thing is to prepare the environment for playing the audio material, in which the listeners provide a quiet environment, and the teacher focuses on the quality of the audio being played and that the sound amplifiers are working well, and the exercises to be performed before and after the audio are played. ready and students should be provided with handouts. After all the requirements are fulfilled, the teacher can start broadcasting the audio material to the students. Listening is done at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material.

All educational material of students of the tourism direction, not as a goal, but as a means of teaching speech (texts used for the development of speech, micro texts for mastering words and speech patterns) also rely on film events, but expand and develop them. Except for the exercises in the stage of development of speech skills, the content of many educational exercises could be determined depending on the situation. The inclusion of the activity context is the main condition for the individualization of situations.

In conclusion, it is a very effective way to show students videos, clips, and discuss them using multimedia in the course of teaching using technology, both in speaking and writing. It is possible to use the vocabulary familiar to the learners, to explain the words if there are new and complex words, and after completing the exercises related to the new words, it is possible to show the video material. In

order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of watching for everyone, and checking that the loudspeakers are working. It follows from this that the role of modern technologies in enriching our lessons, interesting students, enriching their knowledge is incomparable. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

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